

Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 2-[5'-Alkyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]amino-benzothiazole, -benzoxazole, -benzimidazole and -imidazolidines

ASHOK K. SHAKYA, R. K. AGRAWAL and PRADEEP MISHRA*

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 008

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Some new 1,3,4-thiadiazolylamino-benzothiazole, -benzoxazole, -benzimidazole and -imidazolidines have been synthesised and screened for their antibacterial activity.

A number of thiazolylamino-benzothiazole, -benzoxazole, -benzimidazole and -imidazolidines is reported to possess promising antibacterial activities¹. In continuation of our work on 1,3,4-thiadiazoles², it was thought worthwhile to synthesise a few 2-[5'-alkyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]amino-benzothiazole, -benzoxazole, -benzimidazole and -imidazolidines and to evaluate these for antibacterial activity.

Reaction of carbon disulphide and methyl iodide with 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1) in the presence of concentrated aqueous sodium hydroxide gave dimethyl-N-[5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]dithiocarbamate (2) which on treatment with bisnucleophiles such as *o*-aminophenol, -benzthiol, *o*-phenylenediamine and ethylenediamine gave 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively.

1; X=NH,
2; X=N=C(SCH₃)₂

3; Y=S
4; Y=O

5; R₁=H
6; R₁=COC₆H₅

7

1-7a; R=CH₃
1-7b; R=C₂H₅
1-7c; R=n-C₄H₉

Experimental

The purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel-G using ethanol-acetic acid-water (5 : 3 : 2). The m.p.s. were determined in open capillaries using a Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer. All the compounds showed characteristic ir bands at 3 320—3 300 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 210, 1 075, 980 and 875 cm⁻¹ (1,3,4-thiadiazole nucleus).

2-Amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (1): It was prepared by the reported method³.

Dimethyl-N-[5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]dithiocarbamate (2): To a well-stirred cold solution of 1a-c (0.05 mol) in dimethylformamide (20 ml), were added aqueous 20 molar NaOH (4.0 ml), carbon disulphide (7.5 ml) and methyl iodide (7.5 ml) in sequence at an interval of 0.5 h and stirring was continued for 2-4 h. The mixture was then poured in cold water and the resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %
2a	163	79
b	118	85
c	150	87
3a	190	78
b	165	61
c	137	62
4a	127	50
b	182	54
c	115	80
5a	137	55
b	112	60
c	165	65
6a	109	89
b	113	51
c	125	65
7a	209	65
b	128	78
c	198	73

*All the compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

2-[5'-Alkyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]amino-benzothiazole and -benzoxazole (4, 3): A solution of 2-aminothiophenol or 2-aminophenol (0.005 mol) in DMF (10 ml) was treated with 5 molar aqueous NaOH (1.0 ml) and the mixture was stirred at room temperature for 0.5 h. A solution of **2** (0.005 mol) in DMF was then added to it dropwise and the mixture refluxed. All the reactions involving 2-aminophenol were carried out in nitrogen atmosphere. After cooling, the mixture was poured into water and neutralised with concentrated HCl. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and under reduced pressure recrystallised from methanol-acetone (3 : 2).

2-[5'-Alkyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]amino-benzimidazole and -substituted-benzimidazole (5, 6): To a solution of *o*-phenylenediamine or *p*-benzoyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (0.004 mol) in DMF (15 ml) was added a solution of **2** (0.005 mol) in DMF (20 ml) with vigorous stirring at room temperature, and the mixture was refluxed for 8–10 h. The mixture was then poured on crushed ice and the resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from methanol.

2-[5'-Alkyl-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-2'-yl]aminoimidazolidines (7): To a solution of ethylenediamine (0.008 mol) in DMF (15 ml), a solution of **2** (0.004 mol) in DMF (15 ml) was added with stirring at room temperature. The reaction mixture was maintained at 100° for 8–10 h, cooled and then ice-cold water was added. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried and recrystallised from acetone.

All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by cup-plate agar diffusion techniques⁴ using 10 µg ml⁻¹ concentration against *E. coli*, *S. typhi*, *V. cholera*, *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis*.

Dimethylformamide was used as control, and penicillin and streptomycin were used as standard.

Results and Discussion

Compounds **6a** and **6c** showed activity against all the bacteria studied except *B. subtilis*. Compound **6b** was effective only against *S. typhi* and *E. coli*. Compound **3b** and **3c** were found to be active only against *S. typhi*. Compound **2c** showed activity against *V. cholera* and *E. coli*.

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